

A new CLARIN Resource Family for lexical semantic change

Final report

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Introduction	2
Appendix A	5
Workflows: how the new CLARIN Resource Family can help lexical semantic change research in different fields	5
Workflow 1: use-case for lexicology.....	6
Workflow details.....	6
Workflow steps.....	8
Step 1:.....	8
Step 2:.....	8
Step 3:.....	8
Step 4:.....	9
Step 5:.....	9
Step 6:.....	10
Workflow 2: use-case for legal scholar.....	10
Workflow details.....	10
Workflow steps.....	12
Step 1:.....	12
Step 2:.....	13
Step 3:.....	13
Step 4:.....	14
Step 5:.....	14
Step 6:.....	15
Workflow 3: use-case for a historian.....	15
Workflow details.....	15
Workflow steps.....	17
Step 1:.....	17
Step 2:.....	18
Step 3:.....	18
Step 4:.....	19
Step 5:.....	19
Step 6:.....	19
Step 7:.....	20
Workflow 4: use-case for cultural history and history of ideas.....	20
Workflow details.....	20
Workflow steps.....	22

Step 1:.....	22
Step 2:.....	23
Step 3:.....	23
Step 4:.....	24
Step 5:.....	24
Step 6:.....	24
Workflow 5: use-case for lexicography for historical and non-historical dictionaries.....	25
Workflow details.....	25
Workflow steps.....	26
Step 1:.....	26
Step 2:.....	27
Step 3:.....	27
Step 4:.....	27
Step 4a:.....	28
Step 5:.....	29
Step 6:.....	29
Workflow 6: use-case for NLP.....	30
Workflow details.....	30
Workflow steps.....	31
Step 1:.....	31
Step 2:.....	32
Step 3:.....	32
Step 4:.....	32
Step 5:.....	33
Step 6:.....	33
Appendix B. Survey on the state of the art.....	34
Appendix C. Preliminary guidelines for manual annotation.....	35
Appendix D. CLARIN Café.....	36
Future plans.....	37
References.....	38

Introduction

This document collects all the outputs produced in the project “A new CLARIN Resource Family for lexical semantic change research”, funded by the CLARIN through the CLARIN Resource Families project for the period from 1/11/2022 to 30/06/2023.

Lexical semantic change (LSC), the linguistic phenomenon by which words change their meanings over time, is of great relevance to humanities and social science research (HSS), with strong connections to concept drift analysis in history, diachronic semantics in historical linguistics, and lexicography. There has been a strong interest in developing computational

methods for the automatic detection of LSC from corpora within the NLP community in recent years, e.g. the dedicated SemEval task (Schlechtweg et al. 2020) on English, Latin, Swedish and German, and further tasks for Italian, Russian and Spanish. In parallel, research on building a linked data model to represent LSC data has developed vocabularies and standards (Armaselu et al. 2022), but a lot remains to be done to make these resources and tools more widely accessible, thus allowing researchers to advance research in LSC change and concept drift.

The aim of this project is to pave the way for the creation of a *new task-oriented CLARIN resource family* (CRF) that brings together existing resources and tools needed to support LSC research. Our main objective is to enable the creation of this CRF by producing documentation supporting and describing it.

Aligned with [CLARIN 2021-2023 strategy](#), the CRF will:

- Enable multilingual LSC research investigating *language as a carrier of cultural content and information*.
- Strengthen CLARIN's role as a pillar supporting HSS research given the central role played by LSC in HSS research.
- Enable LSC detection algorithms on multilingual language resources, facilitating advancement in *language technology research*.
- *Improve discoverability of existing tools and CRFs*. LSC research requires different language resources and tools: annotated corpora, dictionaries, language models and LSC detection algorithm. Some are available within CLARIN, scattered across different CRFs: the [Historical Corpora CRF](#), the [Annotated Corpora CRF](#) and the [Dictionaries CRF](#). New CRFs on language models and Linguistic Linked Open Data in the context of the [LiLa project](#) are being planned. What is missing is a way to combine all these existing resources with LSC-specific ones, to enable HSS and computational linguistics researchers to advance LSC research. This project aims to address this gap.

The prospective CRF will contain the following types of datasets:

- a) Lexical semantic annotation datasets. These consist of snippets of diachronic corpora containing a set of target words and annotated at the level of lexical semantics, for example with reference to dictionary definitions or WordNet synsets. An example is the SemEval [Latin annotated dataset](#) or the Ancient Greek dataset (Vatri and Lähteenoja 2019). These datasets can serve as training or evaluation sets of lexical semantic change detection algorithms as done in Schlechtweg et al. (2020) or can be used for corpus studies on lexical semantics, as in McGillivray et al. (2022).
- b) Trained word embeddings from diachronic corpora, either word type or word token embeddings (contextualised embeddings). An example is the [Latin lemma embeddings](#) (Sprugnoli et al. 2021). These datasets are critical to any algorithm that uses distributional information (i.e. data about words' corpus co-occurrence) to derive semantic representations of words for further quantitative processing.
- c) Tools for semantic change detection: These are algorithms such as the ones developed in the SemEval 2020 shared task (Schlechtweg et al. 2020).

- d) Computational lexical resources which provide the sense inventories for annotating the corpora in a); these can be digitised versions of legacy resources with IDs for individual senses or wordnets.
- e) Structured datasets describing lexical etymologies using standard vocabularies (Khan 2018). An example is the LiLa representation of the etymological content of de Vaan Etymological Dictionary of Latin as a series of RDF graphs (Mambrini and Passarotti 2020).

In order to show how all the resources and datasets listed in a)-e) can be combined to aid lexical semantic change research, we propose six different workflows (see Appendix A). The workflows that we present follow the model adopted in the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace, and develop a research process involving lexical semantic change for six different research fields. We propose that CLARIN also adopts the idea of hosting workflows, with various links to already existing CLARIN resources: workflows effectively communicate the usefulness not only of the new CRF for lexical semantic change research, but also of existing ones that could be grouped under the new one.

In the project proposal, we promised the following outputs:

1. A **report** outlining the state of the art in lexical semantic annotation of diachronic corpora, including relevant tools and resources for LSC detection. The report will include an outline of **annotation guidelines** for diachronic lexical semantics of Latin and ancient Greek. This will form the basis of a collaborative community effort to build a general set of guidelines applicable to other languages.
2. A **paper** submitted to the 2023 CLARIN annual conference presenting the results of the project. The paper will describe the CRF, with a **case study** on the medical Latin lexicon.
3. A **CLARIN Café online event** to promote the CRF and solicit contributions from the CLARIN community to cover further languages. The event will be accompanied by a **tutorial document** explaining how the components of the CRF can be used for LSC research for the CLARIN website. To facilitate the addition of further languages, the project's documentation will be designed to be as accessible and general as possible, to allow other researchers outside the project to contribute to the initiative in the future.

These outputs will be added to this document in the Appendix B (report on the state of the art), C (annotation guidelines), and D (CLARIN Café tutorial document and slides).

A paper titled "A new CLARIN Resource Family for lexical semantic change research" was submitted for the CLARIN annual conference "CLARIN 2023", on 16-18 October 2023 in Leuven, Belgium. The paper illustrates our plan for the creation of the new CRF with a case study on Latin.

Appendix A.

Workflows: how the new CLARIN Resource Family can help lexical semantic change research in different fields

This Appendix hosts the description of six different workflows that illustrate how the prospective CLARIN Resource Family can help lexical semantic change research in different research fields.

To create the six workflows we followed the structure of the workflows offered by the platform Social Sciences & Humanities Open Marketplace (SSH Open Marketplace), available at <https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/search?categories=workflow>. The workflows offered in SSH Open Marketplace aim at describing the process of creating a new resource e.g. a digital edition (<https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/bKefY4>), or performing a specific type of analysis e.g. on intertextuality in European drama history (<https://marketplace.sshopencloud.eu/workflow/DMJlzG>), by dividing it into a sequence of steps. Each step corresponds to a specific task which is further described and may be linked to a series of resources, including tools, softwares, manuals or reference literature that is relevant to the task. The underlying idea is to make the workflow as accessible and understandable as possible for the intended audience, and to connect different resources that are already available on the SSH Open Marketplace and show how they can be combined to target specific research outputs.

SSH Open Marketplace offers a workflow template, which guides the creator(s) through the steps of the conception of the workflow. The template includes informations such as i) the context of the workflow i.e., the research field and the research questions to which it refers; ii) the online or offline resources which will be given as references to the audience; iii) other complementary information such as the type of licence for the resource, the names of the creators, the specific keywords, the intended audience etc.

We used the templates provided by SSH Open Marketplace to elaborate our proposal of adding a similar resource in CLARIN. We believe that showing the audience how the resources that CLARIN already offers can be applied to a specific research question can enhance the impact of the already existing CRFs, and pave the way for the creation of the future CRF for lexical semantic change research. In this Appendix A we will refer to research fields that are very different from each other but which all have in common research on lexical semantic change as a tool for answering their own research questions. The workflows we will show below in this section will serve to demonstrate how various resources already present in CLARIN and scattered across different CRFs can serve to answer research questions from different fields, and consequently how a specific CRF for lexical semantic change research can have a major impact on the scientific community.

Before showcasing our workflows, we must point out that in some cases the study of changes of meaning may focus on the distinction between genres and/or contexts of use rather than on diachrony. In these cases we will speak of semantic shift rather than semantic change, as the latter is often used specifically to refer to diachronic change (Koptjevskaja-Tamm 2016: 1).

There is also another point that should be clarified, and which we have not deepened in the description of workflows. Each one of the workflows listed below includes a step for lexical semantic change detection by using distributional semantic models. However, this step implies a sequence of sub-steps to define what type of algorithm is best suited for a specific type of research; to determine the best combination of parameters; to train and run the algorithm. Many different approaches exist with respect to this. Traditional word embedding approaches work at the token level (Mikolov et al., 2013; Pennington et al., 2014), that is, are trained on the word forms in the corpus. However, research on lexical semantic change might benefit from lemma embeddings, i.e., algorithms trained on the lemmatised corpus (Kuznetsov & Gurevytch, 2018). Moreover, the approaches may vary between contextualised or non-contextualized embeddings and type of change detection measure e.g., Cosine Distance or Local Neighborhood Distance (Sprugnoli et al. 2020: 33).

Workflow 1: use-case for lexicology

Workflow details

Field's name	
label	Semantic change analysis for lexicological studies
Description	A lexicologist wants to study the evolution of a lexical or semantic field. For instance, a lexicologist studying Latin might be interested in the medical lexicon, and they want to know how words in the Latin medical lexicon have changed their meaning from a more general to a more specialised one. Another Latin lexicologist might be interested in semantic lexical changes related to large-scale social and historical events, such as the advent of Christianity. Starting with a specific semantic field and a list of words associated with it, they need to determine which words have changed their meaning and which new senses they have acquired or lost, or which of their meanings have undergone some other type of semantic change. This type of study can be carried out by using various resources, including those already available in CLARIN. However, these resources are currently scattered across different CLARIN Resource Families, and do not have enough visibility for people who work on lexical semantic change in different fields. This task would hugely benefit from the creation of a new CLARIN Resource Family for Lexical Semantic Change (LSC), which would collect all existing resources (and possibly new ones) that could be employed for the study of LSC in this scenario. This workflow aims at illustrating how such a new CRF

	could be used for applications in lexical semantic change, by taking the work of a lexicologist on a semantic field as a use-case.
Actors	Authors: Paola Marongiu; Fahad Khan; Barbara McGillivray
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevant CLARIN Resource Families: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/historical-corpora ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/manually-annotated-corpora ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/dictionaries ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/lexical-resources-lexica ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/lexical-resources-wordlists ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/lexical-resources-conceptual-resources ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/lexical-resources-glossaries ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/language-models ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/corpus-query-tools

CATEGORISATION metadata

Activity (based on TaDiRAH)	Discovering; Extracting
keyword	semantic-change
Discipline (based on ÖFOS 2012)	Linguistics
Language (based on ISO 639-3)	English

licence	CC-BY-1.0
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Intended audience	Researcher https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/sshoc-audience/en/page/researcher
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Resource category	Data Analysis https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/eosc-resource-category/en/page/subcategory-processing-and-analysis-data-analysis-image-data-analysis
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Workflow steps

Step 1:

Description	The first step is for the researcher to set up a corpus (a collection of texts) to perform their analysis on a reference corpus for the target language. Such a corpus should capture variation on the axes that the researcher intends to study e.g. it should be diachronic, or contain texts belonging to different genres or disciplines and this information should ideally be available via the metadata describing each of the texts in the corpus. This corpus does not necessarily need to be sense-annotated, but it should be lemmatised and PoS tagged to reduce data sparsity.
label	Set up a corpus
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CLARIN Resource Families: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/historical-corpora ◦ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/manually-annotated-corpora • References: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Hilpert, Martin, and Stefan Th Gries. 2016. Quantitative approaches to diachronic corpus linguistics. In Kytö, Merja, and Päivi Pahta, eds. <i>The Cambridge handbook of English historical linguistics</i>. Cambridge University Press: 36-53.

Step 2:

label	Split the corpus into different spans
Description	In order to be able to capture semantic changes, the researcher needs to have the data in the corpus divided into different spans. If the researcher wants to capture diachronic semantic change, they will need to split the corpus into diachronic spans, the size of which will depend on the type of change to be captured. If, on the other hand, the type of change concerns the specialised use of words from everyday language in the technical language of a certain discipline, the segmentation of the corpus will be based rather on the type of texts and their genre (specialist and non-specialist texts).
Related items	

Step 3:

label	Train word embeddings on different spans
Description	The lexicologist can use word embedding algorithms to determine if and how the semantics of a certain word has shifted and has acquired another sense in a

	different domain or diachronic span. In order to do this, the lexicologist trains word embeddings on the different sub-corpora or the different diachronic spans obtained in step 2.
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CLARIN Resource Families: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/language-models

Step 4:

label	Evaluation against a Gold Standard
Description	<p>The NLP researcher will need to evaluate the algorithm against the state of the art. In order to do that, they can use existing Gold Standards or create another one for the specific task. In order to create a Gold Standard for the evaluation, they will need to create a manually annotated dataset of lexical word senses for the languages included in the study.</p> <p>The manual annotation has to be performed by following specific <u>annotation guidelines for manual annotation of word senses</u> (see Appendix C).</p> <p>As an output, the NLP researcher will obtain a dataset of occurrences of the target words in context, manually annotated with senses. This dataset can then be used to evaluate the performance of the algorithm.</p>
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dominik Schlechtweg, Barbara McGillivray, Simon Hengchen, Haim Dubossarsky, and Nina Tahmasebi. 2020. SemEval-2020 Task 1: Unsupervised Lexical Semantic Change Detection. In <i>Proceedings of the Fourteenth Workshop on Semantic Evaluation</i>, pages 1–23, Barcelona (online). International Committee for Computational Linguistics. <p>Example of annotation guidelines for lexical sense annotation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paola Marongiu, & Barbara McGillivray. (2023). Preliminary guidelines for manual annotation of word senses in Latin and ancient Greek corpora. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7576676

Step 5:

label	Qualitative analysis of the results of the word embeddings
Description	The researcher compares the closest neighbours of the target words in different time spans in order to determine how the word has changed based on words that occur in similar contexts
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sprugnoli, Moretti and Passarotti 2020 https://journals.openedition.org/ijcol/624 • Ribary and McGillivray 2020 https://www.mdpi.com/2227-9709/7/4/44

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rodda, Probert, McGillivray 2019 https://www.repository.cam.ac.uk/items/c3695d20-0798-495c-a4bd-b83a5b7e5140
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Step 6:

label	Additional analysis: qualify the type of semantic change
Description	The researcher analyses the results of the word embeddings and determines what kind of semantic change affected the words under study, based on literature and studies on semantic change.
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> References: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Juvonen, P- and Koptjevskaja-Tamm, M. (Eds.). (2014) <i>The lexical typology of semantic shifts</i>. Berlin, Boston: Mouton de Gruyter.

Workflow 2: use-case for legal scholar

Workflow details

Field's name	
label	Semantic shift analysis for legal studies
Description	<p>A legal scholar wants to study the organisation of a specific legal system, and the evolution of legal concepts. In order to do this, they start with a list of words that belong to the legal lexicon and study the evolution of their semantics from the common use to their specialised legal sense. For instance, the Latin adjective <i>aequus</i> shows a specialisation of meaning in the legal context, going from the general meanings 'flat', 'equal', 'similar' to the legal meaning 'fair, just, reasonable, right' (Ribary and McGillivray 2020: 20). This shift can be detected by using word embeddings on a general and a specialised corpus and comparing their results.</p> <p>This type of study can be carried out by using various resources, including those already available in CLARIN. However, these resources are currently scattered across different CLARIN Resource Families, and do not have enough visibility for people who work on lexical semantic change in different fields. This task would hugely benefit from the creation of a new CLARIN Resource Family for Lexical Semantic Change (LSC), which would collect all existing resources (and possibly new ones) that could be employed for the study of LSC in this scenario. This workflow aims at illustrating how such a new CRF could be used for applications in lexical semantic change, by taking the work of a legal scholar as a use-case.</p>

Actors	Authors: Paola Marongiu; Fahad Khan; Barbara McGillivray
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Relevant CLARIN Resource Families: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/historical-corpora ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/manually-annotated-corpora ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/dictionaries ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/lexical-resources-lexica ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/lexical-resources-wordlists ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/lexical-resources-conceptual-resources ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/lexical-resources-glossaries ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/language-models ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/corpus-query-tools ● Reference paper for this workflow: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Ribary, Marton, and Barbara McGillivray. 2020. "A Corpus Approach to Roman Law Based on Justinian's Digest" <i>Informatics</i> 7, no. 4: 44. https://doi.org/10.3390/informatics7040044

CATEGORISATION metadata

Activity (based on TaDiRAH)	Discovering; Extracting
keyword	semantic-change
Discipline (based on ÖFOS 2012)	Law
Language (based on ISO 639-3)	English
licence	CC-BY-1.0
Intended audience	Researcher https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/sshoc-audience/en/page/researcher
Resource category	Data Analysis https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/eosc-resource-category/en/page/subcategory-processing-and-analysis-data-analysis-image-data-analysis

Workflow steps

Step 1:

Description	<p>A legal scholar needs to set up a corpus (a collection of texts) to perform their analysis on a reference corpus for a given language to see which words were used with a legal meaning compared to the common usages (e.g. in Latin <i>aetas</i> shifting from indicating a stage of life in the general corpus to indicating a specific condition limiting legal capacity; <i>aequus</i> from the concept of flatness or similarity to the concept of justice, equality; <i>infans</i> from 'infant, child' to 'underage, not having the power of speech' see Ribary and McGillivray 2020: 20). Such a corpus should capture variation on the axis involved in this type of study. That is, it should capture variation by genre i.e., legal texts vs. reference samples of non legal texts.</p> <p>The corpus does not necessarily need to be annotated with word senses but it should be lemmatised and PoS tagged. The texts in the corpus should also come with a sufficiently rich set of metadata describing them (author, date, genre, publisher, address etc.). This allows the researcher to perform the next step i.e., splitting the corpus in order to compare legal texts with a reference sample of non legal texts representing general language.</p> <p>Another option is that the scholar selects two different corpora, roughly comparable by size, one consisting of legal texts (e.g. the <i>Digest</i>) and the other for samples of non-specialised language (e.g. LatinISE).</p>
label	Set up a corpus
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CLARIN Resource Families: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/historical-corpora ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/manually-annotated-corpora ● References: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Hilpert, Martin, and Stefan Th Gries. 2016. Quantitative approaches to diachronic corpus linguistics. In Kytö, Merja, and Päivi Pahta, eds. <i>The Cambridge handbook of English historical linguistics</i>. Cambridge University Press: 36-53. ○ Ribary, Marton, and Barbara McGillivray. 2020. "A Corpus Approach to Roman Law Based on Justinian's Digest" <i>Informatics</i> 7, no. 4: 44. https://doi.org/10.3390/informatics7040044 ○ McGillivray, B. & Kilgarriff, A. (2013). Tools for historical corpus research, and a corpus of Latin, in: P. Bennett, M. Durrell, S. Scheible, R. J. Whitt (Eds.), <i>New Methods in Historical Corpus Linguistics</i>. Narr, Tübingen, 2013. ○ Ribary, M. A Relational Database on Roman Law Based on

	Justinian's Digest. J. Open Humanit. Data 2020, 6, 1-5. https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.12333290
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Step 2:

label	Split the corpus into different spans
Description	<p>In order to be able to capture semantic changes in the legal lexicon, the researcher needs to organise the texts in the corpus to capture specific types of semantic change. If the researcher wants to determine if and how legal terms were borrowed from the non-specialised lexicon and developed a specific legal meaning in legal texts, they will need to organise their corpus and split it into two different sub-corpora: a non-specialised sub-corpus containing texts that do not belong to the legal domain, and ideally balanced between different genres and authors; a specialised corpus of legal texts.</p> <p>The two can be combined: the legal scholar can decide to have two diachronic sub-corpora, one for the non-specialised language and the other for the legal domain.</p>
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/historical-corpora • Example of legal corpus (Digest) https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.12333290 • Example of non-specialised corpus (LatinISE) http://hdl.handle.net/11372/LRT-3170

Step 3:

label	Train word embeddings on different corpora or sub-corpora
Description	<p>At this point, the legal scholar will be able to use word embedding algorithms to determine if and how the semantics of a certain word have shifted with the word acquiring another sense in a different domain.</p> <p>In order to achieve this, the word embedding algorithm should be trained on the two sub-corpora or the two corpora that represent, respectively, legal language and non-specialised language.</p>
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/language-models • Ribary, M. pyDigest, A GitLab Repository of Scripts, Files and Documentation. Available online: https://gitlab.eps.surrey.ac.uk/mr0048/pydigest (accessed on 9 September 2020)

Step 4:

label	Set up a Gold Standard
Description	In order to measure if words have changed from non-specialised to specialised language, the legal scholar will need to set up a Gold Standard to evaluate the performance of the algorithm. Gold standards for the evaluation of word embeddings already exist (see e.g. Sprugnoli et al. 2020 for Latin; Schlechtweg et al. 2020). But depending on the type of research the scholar is intending to carry out they may need to create their own Gold Standard. For instance, to evaluate the performance of the algorithm with the synonym selection task, the legal scholar will need a Gold Standard of the closest synonyms of the target words being studied. Such a synonym set can be built by using dictionaries of synonyms and/or lexical resources for the target language.
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Lexical resources for the GS:<ul style="list-style-type: none">◦ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/dictionaries• Existing GS:<ul style="list-style-type: none">◦ Latin : Lila benchmark https://github.com/CIRCSE/Lemma-Embeddings-for-Latin◦ legal Latin: Ribary, M. pyDigest, A GitLab Repository of Scripts, Files and Documentation. Available online: https://gitlab.eps.surrey.ac.uk/mr0048/pydigest (accessed on 9 September 2020)◦ English, German, Latin, Swedish: https://www.ims.uni-stuttgart.de/en/research/resources/corpora/sem-eval-ulscd/ from Dominik Schlechtweg, Barbara McGillivray, Simon Hengchen, Haim Dubossarsky, and Nina Tahmasebi. 2020. SemEval-2020 Task 1: Unsupervised Lexical Semantic Change Detection. In <i>Proceedings of the Fourteenth Workshop on Semantic Evaluation</i>, pages 1–23, Barcelona (online). International Committee for Computational Linguistics

Step 5:

label	Measure semantic shift
Description	The legal scholar, based on the performance of the algorithm on the Gold Standards for non-specialised and specialised language, is able to measure how the word has changed between the two corpora (or sub-corpora).
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Literature about using GS for measuring change:<ul style="list-style-type: none">◦ Sprugnoli, Moretti and Passarotti 2020 https://journals.openedition.org/ijcol/624

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Ribary and McGillivray 2020 https://www.mdpi.com/2227-9709/7/4/44 ○ Dominik Schlechtweg, Barbara McGillivray, Simon Hengchen, Haim Dubossarsky, and Nina Tahmasebi. 2020. SemEval-2020 Task 1: Unsupervised Lexical Semantic Change Detection. In <i>Proceedings of the Fourteenth Workshop on Semantic Evaluation</i>, pages 1–23, Barcelona (online). International Committee for Computational Linguistics
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Step 6:

label	Qualify the type of semantic shift
Description	Once the legal scholar has determined that some words' semantics has shifted from the non-specialised (sub-)corpus to the legal (sub-)corpus, they will also be interested in determining the nature of the semantic shift that has occurred. This includes determining both what type of sense the target word has acquired in the legal domain, and what type of semantic change (e.g. narrowing, metaphoric) can be identified. This type of analysis can be performed by inspecting the closest neighbours detected by the algorithm in step 3. Based on this information, the legal scholar is able to determine in which contexts the word that has acquired a new meaning in the legal domain occurs in the latter.
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Example of analyses for Latin legal lexicon: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Ribary and McGillivray 2020 https://www.mdpi.com/2227-9709/7/4/44 ● Example of analyses for non-specialised Latin. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sprugnoli, Moretti and Passarotti 2020 https://journals.openedition.org/ijcol/624 ● References for lexical semantic change: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Juvonen, P- and Koptjevskaja-Tamm, M. (Eds.). (2014) <i>The lexical typology of semantic shifts</i>. Berlin, Boston: Mouton de Gruyter.

Workflow 3: use-case for a historian

Workflow details

Field's name	
label	Tracing diachronic semantic change for historical studies

Description	<p>A historian wants to study a historical phenomenon, the evidence for which is potentially reflected in the way that the semantics of words change over time in a relevant corpus of texts. An example is the study of the role of newspapers in the discussion around the abolition of slavery in the USA and related social justice matters (Soni et al., 2021: 26). More specifically, the introduction of semantic shifts by specific newspapers may have steered the discussion and the audience towards certain views rather than others. It has been found that e.g. the term <i>freedom</i> has shifted from a general abstract sense of an ideal to a more concrete use of this term as a fundamental right (Soni et al. 2021: 26).</p> <p>In order to perform a study of this type, the historian may define a list of terms that are relevant to the domain and concept of phenomenon that they are studying. In order to determine if and how these terms have changed, they can use newspapers, letters or other types of written texts, and measure semantic change with computational resources such as word embedding algorithms.</p> <p>This type of study can be carried out by using various resources, including those already available in CLARIN. However, these resources are currently scattered across different CLARIN Resource Families, and do not have enough visibility for people who work on lexical semantic change in different fields. This task would hugely benefit from the creation of a new CLARIN Resource Family for Lexical Semantic Change (LSC), which would collect all existing resources (and possibly new ones) that could be employed for the study of LSC in this scenario. This workflow aims at illustrating how such a new CRF could be used for applications in lexical semantic change, by taking the work of a historian as a use-case.</p>
Actors	<p>Authors: Paola Marongiu; Fahad Khan; Barbara McGillivray Reviewers: Sandeep Soni, Lauren Klein, Jacob Eisenstein, Dani Roytburg</p>
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reference CLARIN Resource Families for this use-case: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/historical-corpora ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/manually-annotated-corpora ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/dictionaries ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/lexical-resources-lexical ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/lexical-resources-wordlists ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/lexical-resources-conceptual-resources ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/lexical-resources-glossaries ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/language-models ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/corpus-query-tools ● Reference paper for this use-case <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Soni, Sandeep, Lauren F. Klein, and Jacob Eisenstein. 2021. "Abolitionist Networks: Modeling Language Change in Nineteenth-Century Activist Newspapers." <i>Journal of Cultural</i>

	<p><i>Analytics</i> 6 (1). https://doi.org/10.22148/001c.18841</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o https://www.publicbooks.org/how-words-lead-to-justice/
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CATEGORISATION metadata

Activity (based on TaDiRAH)	Discovering; Extracting
keyword	semantic-change
Discipline (based on ÖFOS 2012)	History
Language (based on ISO 639-3)	English

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Intended audience	<p>Researcher</p> <p>https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/sshoc-audience/en/page/researcher</p>
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Resource category	<p>Data Analysis</p> <p>https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/eosc-resource-category/en/page/subcategory-processing_and_analysis-data_analysis-image_data_analysis</p>
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Workflow steps

Step 1:

Description	<p>The historian sets up a collection of texts to perform the analysis. The corpus can be a collection of various types of written texts, such as letters, newspaper articles, chronicles etc.</p> <p>The corpus does not necessarily need to be annotated with senses, but it should be lemmatised and PoS tagged. The texts in the corpus should also come with a sufficiently rich set of metadata describing them (author, date, genre, publisher, address etc.). This allows the researcher to perform the next step i.e., splitting the corpus according to the chronological spans that are useful for the analysis.</p>
label	Set up a collection of texts
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Among CLARIN Resource Families: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/historical-corpora

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/manually-annotated-corpora ● References: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Hilpert, Martin, and Stefan Th Gries. 2016. Quantitative approaches to diachronic corpus linguistics. In Kytö, Merja, and Päivi Pahta, eds. <i>The Cambridge handbook of English historical linguistics</i>. Cambridge University Press: 36-53.
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Step 2:

label	Split the collection of texts into different spans
Description	<p>The historian splits the corpus according to different types of variables, depending on the perspective adopted for the analysis. This could be a specific chronological segmentation or by other variables such as genre or text register , or a combination of the two.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Time spans for diachronic analysis ● Type of source for synchronic analysis <p>An example of selection based on the type of source is given in Soni et al. (2021), where newspapers edited by black and white women are selected.</p>
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Among CLARIN Resource Families: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/historical-corpora ● References: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ David Bamman, Chris Dyer, and Noah A Smith, (2014) "Distributed representations of geographically situated language," in Proceedings of the 52nd Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 2: Short Papers) (2014), 828–34.

Step 3:

label	Train word embeddings on different spans
Description	Word embedding algorithms are trained on the sub-corpora corresponding to different spans to determine which terms have changed their meaning over time.
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CLARIN Resource Family relevant for this step: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/language-models ● Literature about different algorithms for semantic change detection: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Dominik Schlechtweg, Barbara McGillivray, Simon Hengchen, Haim Dubossarsky, and Nina Tahmasebi. 2020. SemEval-2020 Task 1: Unsupervised Lexical Semantic Change Detection. In <i>Proceedings of the Fourteenth Workshop on Semantic Evaluation</i>,

	<p>pages 1–23, Barcelona (online). International Committee for Computational Linguistics.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Tahmasebi, Nina, Lars Borin, and Adam Jatowt. "Survey of computational approaches to lexical semantic change detection." <i>Computational approaches to semantic change</i> 6 (2021): 1 ○ Andrey Kutuzov, Lilja Øvrelid, Terrence Szymanski, and Erik Velldal. 2018. Diachronic word embeddings and semantic shifts: A survey. In Proceedings of the 27th International Conference on Computational Linguistics, pages 1384–1397, Santa Fe, New Mexico, USA. Association for Computational Linguistics.
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Step 4:

label	Measure change
Description	In order to detect which words have substantially changed their meaning over time, the historian can compute the similarity between the neighbours of a word in different diachronic stages, and based on this measure, they can determine which words should be subjected to a closer analysis.
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● References for measuring semantic change: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Soni, Sandeep, Lauren F. Klein, and Jacob Eisenstein. 2021. "Abolitionist Networks: Modeling Language Change in Nineteenth-Century Activist Newspapers." <i>Journal of Cultural Analytics</i> 6 (1). https://doi.org/10.22148/001c.18841 (see pages 11–13)

Step 5:

label	Determine how specific words have changed through time
Description	Besides measuring semantic change, the historian can rely on a closer analysis of the closest neighbours for each (or a selection of) target words, to determine how a certain word has changed its semantics and towards which semantic field and/or meaning.
Related items	

Step 6:

label	Identify the source of the semantic change
Description	From the perspective of an historian, it is often important to know not only which words have changed and to categorise the kind of change which has taken place,

	<p>but also to determine whether a given instance of semantic change was originally introduced by a specific historic source, or type of historic source. This could be a specific newspaper, a group of newspapers edited by people belonging to a certain socio-economic category, a specific person etc.</p> <p>In order to extract this type of information the historian can identify so-called 'leaders' that introduced the semantic change that 'followers' have contributed spreading across many other different types of sources. Leaders can be identified by exploiting the metadata defined in step 1 and determining the type of source associated with a certain word that has changed.</p>
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● References for associating a certain semantic change to a leader: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Soni, Sandeep, Lauren F. Klein, and Jacob Eisenstein. 2021. "Abolitionist Networks: Modeling Language Change in Nineteenth-Century Activist Newspapers." <i>Journal of Cultural Analytics</i> 6 (1). https://doi.org/10.22148/001c.18841 (see pages 13–15)

Step 7:

label	Determine how semantic change relates to historical settings by using quantitative or qualitative methods
Description	The information extracted in the previous steps can be used for further analysis to determine e.g. tendencies of semantic change or common traits of the leaders that were found to have introduced instances of semantic change.
Related items	

Workflow 4: use-case for cultural history and history of ideas

Workflow details

Field's name	
label	Semantic change analysis for cultural history and the history of ideas
Description	A historian of ideas wants to trace the evolution of conceptual constructs through time. An example is the study of how the concept of 'nation' has changed through time e.g. between 1840 and 1920 and across different languages

	<p>(Verheul et al. 2022). In order to do this, the historian establishes a list of words that are linked to the concept that is being studied. In the case of the concept of nation, the list may include country names and terms like ‘people’, ‘independence’, ‘mankind’, ‘monarchy’, ‘democracy’ and others. Then, the historian can use a diachronic corpus to trace patterns of semantic change for the words associated with the target concept.</p> <p>This type of study can be carried out by using various resources, including those already available in CLARIN. However, these resources are currently scattered across different CLARIN Resource Families, and do not have enough visibility for people who work on lexical semantic change in different fields. This task would hugely benefit from the creation of a new CLARIN Resource Family for Lexical Semantic Change (LSC), which would collect all existing resources (and possibly new ones) that could be employed for the study of LSC in this scenario. This workflow aims at illustrating how such a new CRF could be used for applications in lexical semantic change, by taking the work of a cultural historian/historian of ideas as a use-case.</p>
Actors	<p>Authors: Paola Marongiu; Fahad Khan; Barbara McGillivray Reviewer: Emily Bell</p>
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CLARIN Resource Families useful for this use-case: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/historical-corpora ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/manually-annotated-corpora ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/dictionaries ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/lexical-resources-lexica ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/lexical-resources-wordlists ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/lexical-resources-conceptual-resources ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/lexical-resources-glossaries ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/language-models ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/corpus-query-tools ● Reference literature for this use-case: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Verheul, Jaap, Hannu Salmi, Martin Riedl, Asko Nivala, Lorella Viola, Jana Keck, and E. J. L. Bell. "Using word vector models to trace conceptual change over time and space in historical newspapers, 1840–1914." <i>Digital Humanities Quarterly</i> 16, no. 2 (2022). ○ Rodman, Emma. "A timely intervention: Tracking the changing meanings of political concepts with word vectors." <i>Political Analysis</i> 28, no. 1 (2020): 87-111.

Activity (based on TaDiRAH)	Discovering; Extracting
keyword	semantic-change
Discipline (based on ÖFOS 2012)	Cultural history
Language (based on ISO 639-3)	English

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Intended audience	Researcher https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/sshoc-audience/en/page/researcher
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Resource category	Data Analysis https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/eosc-resource-category/en/page/subcategory-processing-and-analysis-data-analysis-image-data-analysis
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Workflow steps

Step 1:

Description	<p>The historian needs to set up a corpus (a collection of texts) to perform their analysis. Such a corpus should capture variation on the axes that the researcher intends to study. For instance it should be diachronic i.e., contain texts from different time periods, to determine if and how certain concepts have evolved through time. If the researcher also wants to determine if the target concepts have evolved the same way or differently in different languages and cultures, they will also need to have a multilingual corpus.</p> <p>The corpus does not necessarily need to be annotated with senses, but it should be lemmatised and PoS tagged in order to reduce data sparsity. The texts in the corpus should also come with a sufficiently rich set of metadata describing them (author, date, genre, publisher, address etc.). This allows for the selection of specific texts for analysis of semantic change on different axes e.g. diachrony and language.</p>
label	Set up a corpus
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CLARIN Resource Families: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/historical-corpora ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/manually-annotated-corp

	<p style="text-align: center;">ora</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● References: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Hilpert, Martin, and Stefan Th Gries. 2016. Quantitative approaches to diachronic corpus linguistics. In Kytö, Merja, and Päivi Pahta, eds. <i>The Cambridge handbook of English historical linguistics</i>. Cambridge University Press: 36-53.
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Step 2:

label	Split the corpus into diachronic spans and/or in different sub-corpora depending e.g. on the source of information
Description	<p>In order to be able to capture semantic changes the historian will need to split the corpus into diachronic spans, the size of which will depend on the type of change to be captured.</p> <p>If the study aims at comparing the evolution of certain concepts in different languages and cultures, the researcher can also opt for splitting the corpus in sub-corpora for different languages, according to some criterion (e.g. specific languages, language families, geographic area, historical reasons etc.).</p>
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/historical-corpora

Step 3:

label	Train word embeddings on different spans
Description	In order to know if and how the target words selected for the study have changed their meaning, the historian can use word embedding algorithms. They can train the algorithm on different time spans and other sub-corpora created in step 2. This way, they will be able to determine if and how the semantics of a certain word or group of words has shifted and has acquired another sense in a different domain.
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CLARIN Resource Families: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/language-models ● References: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Wevers and Koolen 2020 Wevers, Melvin, and Marijn Koolen. 2020. "Digital Begriffsgeschichte: Tracing Semantic Change Using Word Embeddings." <i>Historical Methods: A Journal of Quantitative and Interdisciplinary History</i>, May, 1-18. https://doi.org/10.1080/01615440.2020.1760157.

Step 4:

label	Measure semantic change
Description	By computing the closest neighbours of the target words in different diachronic spans, the historian is able to determine which words have significantly changed their meaning over time. The same type of measure can be applied to the results of the algorithm on other types of segmentation, such as by language or type of source.
Related items	Dominik Schlechtweg, Barbara McGillivray, Simon Hengchen, Haim Dubossarsky, and Nina Tahmasebi. 2020. SemEval-2020 Task 1: Unsupervised Lexical Semantic Change Detection . In <i>Proceedings of the Fourteenth Workshop on Semantic Evaluation</i> , pages 1–23, Barcelona (online). International Committee for Computational Linguistics. Pages 6–7

Step 5:

label	Additional analysis: qualify the semantic change
Description	The researcher analyses the results of the word embeddings and determines what kind of semantic change affected the words under study, based on a closer analysis of the closest neighbours emerged from the application of word embedding algorithms to the diachronic corpus.
Related items	

Step 6:

label	Determine whether and how the conceptual construct has changed
Description	Based on the information obtained throughout the steps 1 to 5, the historian determines how the conceptual construct to which the list of target word is associated has changed through time and/or languages
Related items	

Workflow 5: use-case for lexicography for historical and non-historical dictionaries

Workflow details

Field's name	
label	Semantic change analysis for lexicographic purposes
Description	<p>A lexicographer is tasked with creating a new entry in a historical dictionary or updating one (or more) existing ones.</p> <p>Starting with an (alphabetic) wordlist, they need to determine</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Which words have changed their meaning through time 2. For those words which have changed their meanings, which new senses they have acquired, lost, and/or, for polysemic words which of their meanings have undergone some type of semantic change. <p>This type of study can be carried out by using various resources, including those already available in CLARIN. However, these resources are currently scattered across different CLARIN Resource Families, and do not have enough visibility for people who work on lexical semantic change in different fields. This task would hugely benefit from the creation of a new CLARIN Resource Family for Lexical Semantic Change (LSC), which would collect all existing resources (and possibly new ones) that could be employed for the study of LSC in this scenario. This workflow aims at illustrating how such a new CRF could be used for applications in lexical semantic change, by taking the work of a lexicographer on a semantic field as a use-case.</p>
Actors	Authors: Paola Marongiu; Fahad Khan; Barbara McGillivray
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CLARIN Resource Families that can be used for this workflow: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/historical-corpora ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/manually-annotated-corpora ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/dictionaries ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/lexical-resources-lexica ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/language-models ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/corpus-query-tools

CATEGORISATION metadata

Activity (based on TaDiRAH)	Discovering; Extracting
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keyword	semantic-change
Discipline (based on ÖFOS 2012)	Lexicography
Language (based on ISO 639-3)	English

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Intended audience	Researcher https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/sshoc-audience/en/page/researcher
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Resource category	Data Analysis https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/eosc-resource-category/en/page/subcategory-processing-and-analysis-data-analysis-image-data-analysis
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Workflow steps

Step 1:

label	Set up a corpus
Description	The lexicographer needs to set up a corpus (a collection of texts) to perform their analysis on a corpus of reference for the target language. Such a corpus should capture variation on the axes that the researcher intends to study e.g. it should be diachronic, and/or contain texts belonging to different genres or disciplines. The corpus does not necessarily need to be sense-annotated, but it should be lemmatised and PoS tagged in order to reduce data sparsity. The texts in the corpus should also come with a sufficiently rich set of metadata describing them (author, date, genre, publisher, address etc.). This allows for the selection of specific texts for analysis of semantic change on different axes e.g. diachrony, genre, author.
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CLARIN Resource Families: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/historical-corpora ◦ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/manually-annotated-corpora • References: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Hilpert, Martin, and Stefan Th Gries. 2016. Quantitative approaches to diachronic corpus linguistics. In Kytö, Merja, and Päivi Pahta, eds. <i>The Cambridge handbook of English historical</i>

	<i>linguistics</i> . Cambridge University Press: 36-53.
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Step 2:

label	Split the corpus into different spans
Description	In order to be able to capture semantic change, the researcher needs to ensure that the data in the corpus can be divided into different spans. If the researcher wants to capture semantic change, they will need to split the corpus in diachronic spans, the size of which will depend on the type of change to be captured. If, on the other hand, the type of change concerns the use of words from everyday language that specialise in the technical language of a certain discipline, the segmentation of the corpus will be based rather on the type of texts and their genre (specialised and non-specialised texts).
Related items	

Step 3:

label	Train lexical semantic change detection algorithms on different spans
Description	In order to know which words have changed meaning through time or when used in specialised contexts, the lexicographer first needs to train the algorithm on the different sections of the corpus as defined in step 2. The lexicographer will use state of the art algorithms to make sure to obtain the best results. The output of the algorithm will highlight which words have changed their meaning through time/in specialised contexts based on corpus data.
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CLARIN Resource Families: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/language-models ● References for this step: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Tahmasebi, Nina, Lars Borin, and Adam Jatowt. "Survey of computational approaches to lexical semantic change detection." <i>Computational approaches to semantic change</i> 6 (2021): 1 ○ Andrey Kutuzov, Lilja Øvrelid, Terrence Szymanski, and Erik Velldal. 2018. Diachronic word embeddings and semantic shifts: A survey. In Proceedings of the 27th International Conference on Computational Linguistics, pages 1384–1397, Santa Fe, New Mexico, USA. Association for Computational Linguistics.

Step 4:

label	Measure semantic change
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Description	The lexicographer measures how the words have changed, based on the output of the algorithm. In order to measure semantic change, the researcher computes the sense frequency distribution for each word to determine how often a word occurs in each of its senses. In order to do this, the lexicographer can resort to datasets annotated with word senses, such as the ones created for the task in lexical semantic change detection in SemEval 2020. An alternative is to create a corpus manually annotated with word senses (step 4a). If, from one diachronic stage to a successive one, the sense frequency distribution reveals that the word has acquired or lost a meaning, the word has undergone lexical semantic change.
Related items	Dominik Schlechtweg, Barbara McGillivray, Simon Hengchen, Haim Dubossarsky, and Nina Tahmasebi. 2020. SemEval-2020 Task 1: Unsupervised Lexical Semantic Change Detection . In <i>Proceedings of the Fourteenth Workshop on Semantic Evaluation</i> , pages 1–23, Barcelona (online). International Committee for Computational Linguistics. Pages 6–7

Step 4a:

label	Create a sense-annotated dataset
Description	<p>The researcher will need to evaluate the algorithm against the state of the art. In order to do that, they can use existing Gold Standards or create another one for the specific task. In order to create a Gold Standard for the evaluation, they will need to create a manually annotated dataset of lexical word senses for the languages included in the study.</p> <p>The manual annotation has to be performed by following specific annotation guidelines for manual annotation of word senses (see Appendix C).</p> <p>As an output, the researcher will obtain a dataset of occurrences of the target words in context, manually annotated with senses. This dataset can then be used to evaluate the performance of the algorithm.</p> <p>The sense annotated corpus can also be used by the lexicographer to extract quotations for the dictionary that illustrate a specific sense of the word.</p>
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dominik Schlechtweg, Barbara McGillivray, Simon Hengchen, Haim Dubossarsky, and Nina Tahmasebi. 2020. SemEval-2020 Task 1: Unsupervised Lexical Semantic Change Detection. In <i>Proceedings of the Fourteenth Workshop on Semantic Evaluation</i>, pages 1–23, Barcelona (online). International Committee for Computational Linguistics. <p>Example of annotation guidelines for lexical sense annotation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paola Marongiu, & Barbara McGillivray. (2023). Preliminary guidelines for manual annotation of word senses in Latin and ancient Greek corpora. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7576676

Step 5:

label	Train word embeddings on the spans/subcorpora
Description	<p>After having determined which words have changed their meaning in the list. The lexicographer needs to know which new meanings they have acquired. In order to do that, the lexicographer can use diachronic word embeddings on the diachronic spans or specialised sections of the corpus and compare the closest neighbours of the target words in the different sections.</p> <p>The first step to perform this task is training the word embedding algorithm on the diachronic spans defined in Step 2.</p>
Related items	<p>CLARIN Resource Families:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/language-models● References for this step:<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Andrey Kutuzov, Lilja Øvrelid, Terrence Szymanski, and Erik Velldal. 2018. Diachronic word embeddings and semantic shifts: A survey. In Proceedings of the 27th International Conference on Computational Linguistics, pages 1384–1397, Santa Fe, New Mexico, USA. Association for Computational Linguistics.

Step 6:

label	Determine new senses: qualitative analysis of closest neighbours
Description	The researcher compares the closest neighbours of the target words in different time spans in order to determine how the word has changed based on words that occur in similar contexts (closest neighbours).
Related items	<p>References for the qualitative analysis of the closest neighbours:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Sprugnoli, Moretti and Passarotti 2020 https://journals.openedition.org/ijcol/624● Ribary and McGillivray 2020 https://www.mdpi.com/2227-9709/7/4/44● Rodda, Probert, McGillivray 2019 https://www.repository.cam.ac.uk/items/c3695d20-0798-495c-a4bd-b83a5b7e5140

Workflow 6: use-case for NLP

Workflow details

Field's name	
label	Semantic change detection and analysis for NLP
Description	<p>An NLP researcher wants to develop a new algorithm for semantic change detection and needs to see how it compares with the state of the art.</p> <p>This type of study can be carried out by using various resources, including those already available in CLARIN. However, these resources are currently scattered across different CLARIN Resource Families, and do not have enough visibility for people who work on lexical semantic change in different fields. This task would hugely benefit from the creation of a new CLARIN Resource Family for Lexical Semantic Change (LSC), which would collect all existing resources (and possibly new ones) that could be employed for the study of LSC in this scenario. This workflow aims at illustrating how such a new CRF could be used for applications in lexical semantic change, by taking the work of an NLP researcher as a use-case.</p>
Actors	Authors: Paola Marongiu; Fahad Khan; Barbara McGillivray
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● CLARIN Resource Families useful for this use-case:<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/historical-corpora○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/manually-annotated-corpora○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/dictionaries○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/lexical-resources-lexical○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/language-models○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/corpus-query-tools● Reference literature on this use-case<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Dominik Schlechtweg, Barbara McGillivray, Simon Hengchen, Haim Dubossarsky, and Nina Tahmasebi. 2020. SemEval-2020 Task 1: Unsupervised Lexical Semantic Change Detection. In <i>Proceedings of the Fourteenth Workshop on Semantic Evaluation</i>, pages 1–23, Barcelona (online). International Committee for Computational Linguistics.

Activity (based on TaDiRAH)	Discovering; Extracting
keyword	semantic-change
Discipline (based on ÖFOS 2012)	Computational linguistics
Language (based on ISO 639-3)	English

licence	CC-BY-1.0
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Intended audience	Researcher https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/sshoc-audience/en/page/researcher
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Resource category	Data Analysis https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/eosc-resource-category/en/page/subcategory-processing-and-analysis-data-analysis-image-data-analysis
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Workflow steps

Step 1:

Description	<p>The researcher needs to set up a corpus (a collection of texts) to train the algorithm and perform their tests. Such corpus should be diachronic, in order to obtain an algorithm that is able to capture diachronic semantic change.</p> <p>The corpus does not necessarily need to be annotated with senses, but it should be lemmatised and PoS tagged to reduce data sparsity. The texts in the corpus should also come with a fairly rich set of metadata describing them (author, date, genre, publisher, address etc.). This allows for the selection of specific texts for analysis of semantic change on different axes e.g. diachrony, genre, author.</p>
label	Set up a corpus
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CLARIN Resource Families: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/historical-corpora ○ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/manually-annotated-corpora ● References <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Hilpert, Martin, and Stefan Th Gries. 2016. Quantitative approaches to diachronic corpus linguistics. In Kytö, Merja, and Päivi Pahta, eds. <i>The Cambridge handbook of English historical</i>

	<i>linguistics</i> . Cambridge University Press: 36-53.
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Step 2:

label	Split the corpus in different spans
Description	In order to be able to capture semantic changes across time, the researcher needs to have the data in the corpus divided in diachronic spans. Each corpus should be large enough to efficiently train a model.
Related items	

Step 3:

label	Train algorithm for lexical semantic change detection on the diachronic spans
Description	In order to test how the algorithm performs on lexical semantic change detection, the NLP researcher first needs to train it on the diachronic subcorpora created in step 2. Then they will have to align the semantic spaces and develop and algorithm that identifies the changes between the two (or more) subcorpora. This could be done by calculating the cosine similarity between the embedding of the same word in the semantic space for time t and the embedding for the same word in the semantic space for time t+1.
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CLARIN Resource Families: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ https://www.clarin.eu/resource-families/language-models • References for this step: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Tahmasebi, Nina, Lars Borin, and Adam Jatowt. "Survey of computational approaches to lexical semantic change detection." <i>Computational approaches to semantic change</i> 6 (2021): 1 ◦ Andrey Kutuzov, Lilja Øvrelid, Terrence Szymanski, and Erik Velldal. 2018. Diachronic word embeddings and semantic shifts: A survey. In Proceedings of the 27th International Conference on Computational Linguistics, pages 1384–1397, Santa Fe, New Mexico, USA. Association for Computational Linguistics.

Step 4:

label	Measure semantic change
Description	The NLP researcher measures how the words have changed, based on the output of the algorithm. In order to measure semantic change, the researcher computes the sense frequency distribution for each word to determine how often a word occurs in each of its senses. If, from one diachronic stage to a

	successive one, the sense frequency distribution reveals that the word has acquired or lost a meaning, the word has undergone lexical semantic change.
Related items	Dominik Schlechtweg, Barbara McGillivray, Simon Hengchen, Haim Dubossarsky, and Nina Tahmasebi. 2020. SemEval-2020 Task 1: Unsupervised Lexical Semantic Change Detection . In <i>Proceedings of the Fourteenth Workshop on Semantic Evaluation</i> , pages 1–23, Barcelona (online). International Committee for Computational Linguistics. Pages 6–7

Step 5:

label	Rank words according to their change score
Description	The researcher ranks the words based on their semantic change score. For this ranking, the researcher takes into account not only words that have gained or lost meanings through time, but also how their sense frequency distribution changes through time.
Related items	

Step 6:

label	Evaluation against a Gold Standard
Description	<p>The NLP researcher will need to evaluate the algorithm against the state of the art. In order to do that, they can use existing Gold Standards or create another one for the specific task. In order to create a Gold Standard for the evaluation, they will need to create a manually annotated dataset of lexical word senses for the languages included in the study.</p> <p>The manual annotation has to be performed by following specific annotation guidelines for manual annotation of word senses (see Appendix C).</p> <p>As an output, the NLP researcher will obtain a dataset of occurrences of the target words in context, manually annotated with senses. This dataset can then be used to evaluate the performance of the algorithm.</p>
Related items	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dominik Schlechtweg, Barbara McGillivray, Simon Hengchen, Haim Dubossarsky, and Nina Tahmasebi. 2020. SemEval-2020 Task 1: Unsupervised Lexical Semantic Change Detection. In <i>Proceedings of the Fourteenth Workshop on Semantic Evaluation</i>, pages 1–23, Barcelona (online). International Committee for Computational Linguistics. <p>Example of annotation guidelines for lexical sense annotation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paola Marongiu, & Barbara McGillivray. (2023). Preliminary guidelines for manual annotation of word senses in Latin and ancient Greek corpora.

Appendix B. Survey on the state of the art

As part of the research outputs of the project we have conducted a survey on the existing tools and resources for lexical semantic change research.

The survey is available on Zenodo:

- Marongiu, Paola, Khan, Fahad, & McGillivray, Barbara. (2023). Tools and resources for diachronic lexical semantic analyses: state of the art. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8103978>

Appendix C. Preliminary guidelines for manual annotation

As described in the workflows shown in Appendix A, a necessary step, common to research workflows in different fields, is to evaluate the performance of the algorithm against a Gold Standard i.e., a dataset of high quality, manually checked, which represents the benchmark for the evaluation of the output of an automatic tool. In the case of lexical semantic change research, the Gold Standard can be a corpus of texts in which words have been manually annotated with senses. The annotation of this type of resource requires a set of guidelines, in order to provide the annotator(s) with rich and detailed instructions on how to perform the annotation, and ensure that the output is as coherent and consistent as possible.

The 'Preliminary guidelines for manual annotation of word senses in Latin and ancient Greek corpora' are available on Zenodo:

- Paola Marongiu, & Barbara McGillivray. (2023). Preliminary guidelines for manual annotation of word senses in Latin and ancient Greek corpora. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7576676>

These guidelines describe how the annotation task should be set up and performed, including:

- How to determine the sense inventory for each word to be manually annotated
- How the annotation would look like
 - Graded annotation
 - Only one sense selection for each word occurrence
- Which tool(s) will be used for the manual annotation
- How to deal with specific annotation challenges
 - Metaphoric senses
 - Vagueness
 - Sense boundaries

The guidelines build on evidence from Latin and Ancient Greek, but they are conceived to be as cross linguistically valid as possible.

Appendix D. CLARIN Café

A CLARIN Café event organised by Barbara McGillivray, Fahad Khand and Paola Marongiu will take place on July 5 2023. The objective of the CLARIN Café is to present our work on the new CLARIN Resource Family for lexical semantic change research, and to bring together other researchers in the field of diachronic semantics.

The program of the CLARIN Café "A new CLARIN Resource Family for Lexical Semantic Change Research" is available at the following address <https://www.clarin.eu/event/2023/clarin-cafe-new-clarin-resource-family-lexical-semantic-change-research>

During the CLARIN Café we will give a presentation outlining our work for the new CRF and will provide the audience with a tutorial document illustrating how the new CRF can help research focusing on lexical semantic change, or using lexical semantic change analysis to answer field-specific research questions.

Both the slides and the tutorial document for the CLARIN Café can be found in Zenodo:

- Marongiu, Paola, Khan, Fahad, & McGillivray, Barbara. (2023, July 1). CLARIN Café "A new CLARIN Resource Family for Lexical Semantic Change research". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8104009>

Future plans

During this project, we aimed to lay the foundation for the development of a new task-oriented CLARIN Resource Family that can support research in lexical semantic change (LSC). This new CRF should bring together existing resources within CLARIN for this type of research, which are currently scattered across various CRFs, as well as incorporate resources that are not yet available within CLARIN.

To set the groundwork, we conducted a survey to assess the current state of resources and methods in LSC research. We also produced guidelines for annotating texts at the word sense level, creating resources that can serve as gold standards and training sets for evaluating and training algorithms for LSC detection.

Additionally, we organised an event to showcase the work done and gather external feedback from other researchers in the field of LSC.

Our plan for the future is to ensure that the work we have done continues within the context of CLARIN and that the new task-oriented CRF for LSC becomes a reality. The approach that we propose to achieve this goal is the development of workflows within CLARIN, modelled after those offered by SSH Open Marketplace. We have proposed some examples in Appendix A. These workflows would serve as a means to connect CLARIN resources within a coherent discourse centred around LSC research and aimed at addressing specific research questions.

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